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THE BENEFIT-SHARING FUND'S GRAINEFIT PROJECT - TOWARDS DELIVERING WHEAT GRAINS THAT BRING NUTRITIONAL BENEFITS

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Wheat is a crucial staple crop in Serbia and worldwide, significantly contributing to food security and nutrition. Modern wheat breeding efforts that have concentrated solely on increasing yields have led to a decrease in genetic diversity. The Benefit-sharing Fund of the International Plant Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture's project GRAINEFIT aims to improve the use and conservation of old neglected wheat varieties and landraces leading to increased availability of diverse nutrient-rich food, food security, reduced adverse impacts to the environment, and enhanced resilience to climate stress factors. One of the key activities that address these objectives was a detailed research of nutritional quality and agronomic performances of 33 Serbian wheat genotypes and their comparison to modern ones in two-year field trials (2021/2022, 2022/2023). Our studies showed that the total phenolics in traditional varieties and landraces were generally higher compared to modern varieties. Largely underutilized traditional varieties contained significant levels of ferulic acid, with some having three times higher levels than modern counterparts. Besides, vanillic, syringic and p-coumaric acid were measured in old varieties, but not in modern ones. Antioxidative potential varied among old and new varieties, with many old varieties demonstrating stronger DPPH radical scavenging activity. We also evaluated the levels of two essential minerals, iron and zinc, in old wheat varieties using a GF-AAS and identified Stara Banatka with the highest ash content, and iron and zinc concentrations. Consuming an average daily portion of bread (166 g) made from this flour could provide about 90% of the recommended daily iron intake, making it a variety suitable for breeding for high mineral content. The agronomic performances of some of these high nutritional quality varieties showed moderately high yields and yield components, good standing ability, resistance to prevalent diseases, indicating that they could be successfully exploited to develop climate-resilient varieties with improved quality.

Keywords: landraces, minerals, nutritional value, old varieties, phenolics, wheat

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